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TABLE OF CONTENT

Editorial	vi		
Foreword	vii		
Notes to Contributors	viii		
A STUDY OF IDEATIONAL METAFUNCTION IN YORUBÁ RIDDLE	1		
—Saka, I. Oyenike			
THE EFFECTIVE USE OF FOLKTALES IN CONFLICT RESOLUTION	19		
—Olakolu, Oluwatoyin Titilayo			
THE ROLE OF RELIGION IN FIGHTING CURRUPTION IN NIGERIA: AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE	33		
—Odeniyi, Ismail Kolawole			
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF PHYSICS STUDENTS IN SELECTED PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RURAL AND URBAN COMMUNITIES IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE	52		
—Ikusika, A., Ayorinde O.O., Aramide, J.O., Olabisi I.O.			
LECTURERS' PERCEPTION OF FACTORS INFLUENCING VIOLENT BEHAVIOUR IN ADOLESCENT: A CASE STUDY OF ADEYEMI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ONDO	68		
—Dr. (Mrs.) C.B. Obasoro, and Mr. S.P. Akingbulu			
THE IMPACT OF SEASONAL CHANGES ON THE ENVIRONMENT: IMPLICZTION ON STUDENT ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	81		
Owoyemi, S.I.; Ojo, M.O.; Akinwande D.D.; —Kayode, G.F. and Adediran B.F.			
CORRUPTION IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR IN NIGERIA; THE NEED FOR ETHICAL VALUE REORIENTATION	94		
—Akeredolu, Olukemi and Odunaiya, Marian Oluyemisi			
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) FOR EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES	108		
—Olawuyi N.J., Olaleke, J.O., and Olawuyi, S.O.			
INFLUENCE OF DEPRESSED ECONOMY ON GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ALIMOSHO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF LAGOS STATE	116		
—Femi Olaiya			
FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR POOR HEALTH HABITS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE	127		
—Mopelola O. Akintoye (Ph.D) and Ayomiposi R. Olakunle			
ENTRENCHING QUALITY EDUCATION, MORAL VALUES AND ETHICS IN HUMAN NATURE IN COMBATING ECONOMIC RECESSION IN NIGERIA	144		
—Olorunmota, O.M.; Olaniyan, O.D.; Oddiah, Clement O. and Olorunmota, T. (Mrs)			
NURSES PERCEPTIONS OF NEUROLOGICAL SERVICES DELIVERY AT THE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE HOSPITAL IBADAN, OYO STATE NIGERIA	159		
—Afolabi, Oluwaseun Ayo			
COMMUNICATION IN SPORTS: A VERITABLE TOOL IN SPORTS DEVELOPMENT	177		
—Abdul, Adekunle Adelaja; Ayanlaja, Adesegun Ola Ajayi, OlusegunAdewale & Ajala, Ayotunde Oluwole			

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NURSES PERCEPTIONS OF NEUROLOGICAL SERVICES DELIVERY AT THE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE HOSPITAL IBADAN, OYO STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study set out to ascertain the staff nurses perception of neurological service delivery at the University College Hospital, Ibadan, in Oyo State. Two null hypotheses were generated for the study. The subjects consisted of twenty five selected staff nurses in the Neurological Department in the University College Hospital. Relevant data were collected by means of structured and well validated interview guide and a survey of available resources for neurological service delivery in the University College Hospital. The null hypotheses generated for the study were test, using chi-square statistical analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings indicated that the staff nurses were faced with challenges of patient education, coping with disruptive behaviours of neurological patients, working environment and resources for effective neurological service delivery. Also, modern equipment for coping with neurological issues in the University College Hospital, are grossly indicated. Based on the findings, it was recommended among other things that in order to enhance job satisfaction and productivity among the staff nurses in the University College Hospital, on the job training programmes, seminars and workshops, attractive salaries, allowances and other fringe benefits should be given promptly to them. While modern equipment should be adequately made available in the Neurological Department in the University College Hospital.

Keywords: Staff Nurses, Perceptions, Neurological Service.

Introduction

It is a truism that health is a major factor in the existence of human beings and without good health, productivity in whatever sphere of activity is at its lowest ebb. Thus, the physical, mental and emotional health of a person is of paramount importance, for sound health is the basis of life, no wonder, WHO in 1948 defined health as a complete state of human well-being socially, mentally and physically not mere absence of diseases. A healthy person is one who looks and feels well, has no illness, infirmity or disease and has enough energy for his daily work and recreational activities. Of all the health care services in teaching or specialized hospitals in Nigeria in the last two decades, none is as challenging as neurological service. Patients with neurological emergencies such as neuroleptic malignant syndrome, serotonin syndrome and psychiatric medication overdose are commonly cared for in intensive care units in such hospitals. As succinctly remarked by Nadler – Mondie (2010), common neurological problems include psychosis, substance abuse and withdrawal, delirium, anxiety, aggression, bipolar disorder, personality disorders and suicidal behaviour or ideation.

The prevalence of neurological disease in Nigeria appears astronomical as symptoms of neurological disorders are common among hospitalized patients. Such symptoms include abnormalities of muscle actesa, such as weakness, paralysis, spasticity or stiffness, involuntary movements, gait disturbance and tetany. Other symptoms of neurological disorders include disturbance of speech and swelling, convulsions, disturbances of general sensation, headache, dizziness, impairment of vision, unconsciousness and hallucinations and delusions. According to Loi and Chin (2011), these neurological disorders are more frequently diagnosed in patients with chronic medical conditions who require hospitalization.

Neurological ailments have been receiving prominent attention of medical personnel in Nigeria, because of all the organs and systems of the body, it is the brain and its associated structures in the nervous system that are of greatest importance to the normal functioning of the body and to the general welfare of the individual. The activities of all

other organs and tissues are being controlled by nervous impulses received from the brain and spinal cord. Also, the brain serves as the coordinating agency for all the nervous activities and it is the seat of consciousness and of all psychic functions related to consciousness. Thus, when a portion of the nervous system is damaged by disease or injury, a corresponding deficit in function ensues, either in the part of the body normally controlled by the damaged structure or in the related activities of the brain.

In Nigerian hospitals, nurses constitute the majority of health care professionals, who are in the forefront of patient care, and have been one of the most involved professional groups in the delivery of actual educative activities and health care services for their patients. It is, however, disheartening that nurses in Nigerian hospitals entrusted with neurological service, have been facing various challenges in performing their duties. Such healthcare delivery challenges for nurses include differentiating neurologic symptoms from medical conditions; coping with ambivalent, boisterous and aggressive neurologic patients with all forms of neurotic habits; the resources with which to work; the working environment; and the leadership styles of the heads of their Departments in the hospitals. These challenges can result in nurse perception of healthcare delivery for such patients as stressful, uncomfortable, unrewarding and difficult (Zulnierenk and Chingenman, 2012). If nurses in Neurological Departments in Nigerian hospitals have specialized training and experience to manage disruptive behaviours including aggressive, agitation and psychotic episodes, their fear and anxiety in coping with their neurologic patients will be drastically reduced. The nurses in acute care settings who are trained in early assessment of disruptive or inappropriate behaviours perceive that they are prepared to intervene more effectively. Also, Bernstein and Saladino (2007), affirmed that strategies used to maintain the patient care environment include use of nonjudgmental, soft, calm voice and slow pace when speaking and maintaining a calm activity level. Based on these submissions, it is quite apparent that such intervention competencies especially in neurological settings will decrease the

likelihood that communication and environmental stimuli will lead to neurologic patient outbursts or unpredictable behaviours.

Despite the fact that nurses are often regarded as the best health care professionals for effective patient education, and health care delivery service to the neurologic patients, their capacity to effectively perform their tasks has been frequently questioned. Park and McMillan (2000), reported that there is a discrepancy between patient educative activities that nurses acknowledge they should carry out and those that they actually carry out. Also, Honan et al., (1993), pointed out that nurses often delegate responsibility to the physicians, when they are uncertain about their role in providing certain information. While Morgan (1990), also recognized that some nurses' reluctance to be involved in patient education may have resulted from the ill-defined responsibility in specific areas of patient education. Furthermore, Park and McMillan (2006), reported that although the majority of nurses in their study believe that patient teaching is a high priority and an important part of nursing practice, they rank it lower than other duties such as physical care, administering medications and writing report in actual practice. It would be deduced from all these submissions that when nurses are adequately trained on how to effectively administer neurologic service, with special focus on how to meet the health care and emotional needs of neurologic patients then their fear and anxiety towards neurologic service will be totally jettisoned.

The professional practice environment of the nurses has significant impact on their neurologic service. Wiskow et al., (2010), described a nursing practice environment as the organizational characteristics of a work setting that facilitates or constrains professional nursing practice. Thus, the working environment generally could be described as the place, condition and surrounding influences in which people carry out an activity. In the case of health care, it refers to a set of concrete or abstract features of an organization related to both the structure and processes in that organization that are perceived by nurses as either facilitating or constraining their professional practice. Klopper et al., (2012), described a healthy practice environment as a

work setting, where policies, procedures and systems are designed in such a manner that they meet the organizational objectives and succeed in personal satisfaction at work.

Nurses' perceptions of their professional environment influence their job satisfaction. Traditional job satisfaction relates to the feeling an individual has about his or her job. It is affected by intrinsic factors such as recognition, work itself or responsibility and extrinsic factors such as working conditions, company policy or salary, which have an influence on job satisfaction. Undoubtedly, nurses seek jobs and stay on the job if physical, social status, economic and security dimensions associated with the conditions of work are satisfactory. If working conditions are not perceived as satisfactory, then turnover can be expected for nurses able to move and psychological withdrawal can be expected for those unable to move. The nurses' professional environment is receiving international interest, because there is a growing consensus that identifying opportunities for improving working conditions in hospitals is essential to maintain adequate staffing, high quality care, nurses' job satisfaction and hence their retention. This study is therefore embarked upon to examine nurses' perceptions of their competencies to assess, provide needed effective care for neurologic patients in University College Hospital, Ibadan, in Oyo State, Nigeria. A study of this nature would bring into limelight the various challenges facing the nurses' in the teaching hospital, while performing their neurologic service, particularly to the admitted neurologic patients in the hospital.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria, which is the most populous nation in sub-Saharan Africa, has been witnessing in recent times, high prevalence of neurological ailments. Neurologic disorders are common among hospitalized patients who are frequently diagnosed with chronic medical conditions and such patients often experience an increased risk of adverse outcomes, related to prolonged length of stay, risk of re-hospitalization and increased hospitalization cost and apparent display of aggression and all forms of disruptive behaviours towards the health care givers.

All these challenges tend to have significant impact on the nurses' job performance. Nurses like other professionals work primarily to earn a livelihood. They also expect secondary satisfaction such as pleasant and conducive working environment, friendly co-workers, interesting work, personal recognition and attractive conditions of service. However, adequate working conditions involve not only appropriate welfare provisions, but also the tools and environment for maximum job performance. It is axiomatic that unsatisfactory working environment and lack of modern equipment, tools and materials to work with would lead to poor nurse morale. This study specifically set out to critically examine the perceptions of nurses in the Neurological Department as regards their service to neurologic patients in the University College Hospital, Ibadan. Also, to identify those constraints to effective job performance in the University College Hospital, with a view to making feasible measures, submissions and recommendations toward alleviating them.

Purpose of the Study

The overall goal of every healthcare organization is to systematically develop and reinforce organizational strategies, structures and processes that improve the organization's effectiveness in achieving quality patient care and employee job satisfaction. As the nurses' work environment is a major determinant of patient and nurse welfare, thus the nurses' professional environment is of positive influence on nursing outcomes. Since the work environment has significant influence on the quality of neurological health care service and patient safety, it becomes highly imperative to have an attractive and supportive workplace that attracts individuals into the health professions, encourages them to remain in the health workforce and enables them to perform effectively.

Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the staff nurses' gender and their perceptions of the various challenges facing them, while delivering their services in the Neurological Department at the University College Hospital.

Ho2: The working experience of the staff nurses is not significantly related to their perception of adequacy of the hospital resources for coping with neurological and behavioural issues of neurologic patients.

Significance of the Study

The prevalence of neurologic ailment in Nigeria, in recent times is becoming high, as evidenced in the diagnosis of many hospitalized patients who experience anxiety and apprehension that result in disruptive behaviours, has necessitated the urgent need for a research of this nature. The nurses who constitute the majority of health care professionals are not only in the forefront of the neurologic patient care, but also are one of the most involved professional groups in the delivery of health care services to the neurologic patients. Thus, the findings of this research, which place high premium on the general perceptions of the staff nurses on their neurological service will go a long way in improving the job performance of the nurses, assigned to the Neurological Departments in the hospitals.

The various healthcare delivery challenges facing the nurses engaged in neurological service, such as differentiating between neurologic symptoms and medical conditions, personality disorders and suicidal behavioural tendencies on the part of neurologic patients, and inadequacy of resources with which to administer health care delivery to the patients that would be identified and addressed in this research with appropriate recommendations would help in making neurological service less stressful to the health care givers.

As nurses usually perceive their professional working environment as often stressful and unfriendly which has negative effects on their job satisfaction and productivity. The findings of this research would shed more light into urgent things to be done by the Government and the Hospital Management Board to make neurological service attractive, highly rewarding and pleasant. It is a truism that an effective nursing manager who consults regularly with the staff nurses and provides positive feedback is crucial in enhancing job satisfaction and productivity among the nurses in the Neurological Department.

Research Methodology

This research specifically set out to examine the nurses' perceptions of neurological service. The study is restricted to University College Hospital, Ibadan in Oyo State, Nigeria, using selected staff nurses in the Neurological Department of University College Hospital, Ibadan. The subjects consisted of twenty five staff nurses who were chosen using variables like gender, age, working experience, professional status and marital status. Also, the Head of Department of Neurology was involved in the study. A well structured and well validated interview guide was developed by the researcher to collect pertinent data for the study. Its face and content validity was determined through the assistance of experts in Tests and Measurement at University of Ibadan. While its reliability was established through test-retest method. The two tests were correlated using Pearson product moment correlation formula. A correlation coefficient of 0.87 obtained, clearly indicated that the instrument is reliable for data collection. The null hypotheses generated for the study were tested using chi-square statistical analysis at 0.05 level of significances to show whether they should be rejected or accepted.

Results

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the staff nurses' gender and their perceptions of the various challenges facing them while delivering their services in the Neurological Department at the University College Hospital.

Table 1: Chi-square Analysis on the Staff Nurses' Gender and their Perception of Challenges facing them in the Neurological Department.

Gender	Challenges				Total	Degree of Freedom (df)	Calculated Chi-square Value (χ^2)	Chi-square Table Value (χ^2)	Level of Significance	Remarks
	Patient Education	Disruptive Behaviour	Working Environment	Working Resources						
Male	1 *(1)	2 (1)	5 (5)	4 (5)	12	3	2.00	7.82	0.05	Not Significant
Female	1 *(1)	1 (2)	6 (6)	5 (4)	13					
Total	2	3	11	9	25					

*Figures in the parentheses are the expected values.

As clearly indicated in Table 1, the calculated chi-square value of 2.00 is less than the critical chi-square table value of 7.82 at 0.05 level of significance, with three degrees of freedom. This vividly shows that there is no significant difference between the staff nurses' gender and their perceptions of the various challenges facing them in the Neurological Department, while delivering their services at the University College Hospital, Ibadan, in Oyo State. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted.

Ho2: The working experience of the staff nurses is not significantly related to their perception of adequacy of the hospital resources for coping with neurological and behavioural issues of neurological patients.

Table 2: Chi-square Analysis on the Staff Nurses' working experience and their perceptions of Adequacy of hospital Resources for Neurological Services.

Working Experience	Adequacy of Resources		Total	Degree of Freedom (df)	Calculated Chi-square Value (χ^2)	Chi-square Table Value (χ^2)	Level of Significance	Remarks
	Very Adequate	Inadequate						
1-10 years	1 *(0)	1 (2)	0 (0)	2				
11-20 years	1 *(0)	1 (2)	0 (0)	2				
21-30 years	3 *(4)	10 (9)	5 (5)	18				
Over 31 years	1 *(0)	1 (2)	1 (1)	3				
Total	6	13	6	25	3.01	12.59	0.05	Not Significant

* Figures in the parentheses are the expected values.

As vividly indicated in Table 2, the calculated chi-square value is 3.01, while the critical chi-square table value is 12.59, at 0.05 level of significance, with six degrees of freedom. This shows that the working experience of the staff nurses is not significantly related to their perceptions of the adequacy of hospital resources for coping with neurological and behavioural issues of neurologic patients. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted. As indicated in Table 2, majority of staff nurses with working experience between 21 and 30 years affirmed that the hospital resources for coping with neurological and behavioural issues of neurologic patients are grossly inadequate in the Neurological Department in the University Teaching College Ibadan.

**Discussion of Findings
Symptoms of Neurologic Ailments.**

The nurses reported that there are various signs or symptoms of neurologic ailments that require the individuals with such symptoms to quickly consult neurologic physicians in teaching or specialist hospitals for proper diagnosis and prompt treatment. These symptoms of neurologic ailments include abnormalities of movement of muscle

action, which could be in form of weakness, paralysis, spasticity or stiffness, involuntary or uncontrollable movements, gait disturbance and tetany, that is a condition in which the muscles become abnormally responsive to stimulation. Other symptoms of neurologic ailments include disturbance of speech and swallowing, convulsions, disturbance of general sensations, headache; dizziness; impairment of vision; unconsciousness; hallucinations which are false sensory experiences, the individual concerned seeming to hear, see, or smell something, when actually his eyes, ears or olfactory organs are not being stimulated in a manner to produce these sensations; and delusions which are false beliefs to which an individual adheres in spite of evidence to the contrary.

**Challenges Facing the Nurses while Performing Neurological Service
(a) The challenge of Patient Education:**

It is an indisputable fact that nurses performing neurological service must be well groomed in patient education. According to Park (2005), patient education is described as formal and informal interactive activities performed by health care professionals, aimed at achieving better health outcomes for patients through the provision of information, knowledge and skills that are necessary for the management of their health and illness concerns.

It is the general belief of nurses that patient education is an important and essential part of their care and should be accorded high premium. In carrying out neurological service effectively, nurses need patient education that will give them direction and information on how to discharge their neurological activities.

In spite of the importance of patient education, this vital service is not accorded high priority in some hospitals. Park (2005), remarked that patient education is often given a lower priority than physical care, even when physical care is considered as not a critical nursing task. A number of studies further reported that insufficient time and inadequate staff have been consistently reported as major constraints to the provision of patient education (Berland, Whyte and Maxwell, 1995; Casey, 1995). As succinctly remarked by Huey and Hartley (1988),

shortage of staff in most hospitals results in fewer nurses being available to patients and the resulting time constraint deterring nurses from being able to provide the care that they believe patients need.

Moreover, many nurses erroneously perceive patient education as an additional educative activity, which is not directly associated with the daily care that they provide in hospitals. All registered nurses, especially those engaged in neurological service need patient education that will give them adequate knowledge, information and improve their skills in attending to the health care delivery to their neurologic patients.

(b) The Challenge of coping with Disruptive behaviours of Neurological patients.

It is the general belief of many nurses that neurological service is highly challenging, onerous, stressful, uncomfortable, herculean and dreadful, due to the various disruptive behaviours of neurologic patients that they are dealing with daily. In the intensive care hospital wards, many hospitalized patients are found to be exhibiting all forms of neurologic problems such as psychosis, substance abuse and withdrawal, boisterousness, temper tantrums, delirium, anxiety, personality disorders, bipolar disorders, aggression and all forms of suicidal behaviours. However, if these nurses are adequately trained on how to cope with the disruptive behaviours of the neurologic patients, their fear and anxiety will be removed. As remarked by Rutledge, Wickman, Drake, Winokur and Loucks (2012), nurses in acute care settings who are trained in early assessment of disruptive or inappropriate behaviours perceive that they are prepared to intervene more effectively.

The nurses who have specialized training and experience to manage disruptive behaviours can use strategies such as non-judgmental, soft, calm voice and slow pace when speaking and with the neurologic patients. There is tendency for such intervention competencies particularly in neurological setting to decrease the likelihood that communication and environmental stimuli will lead to patient outbursts or unpredictable behaviours. According to Schleifer (2011), patients experiencing acute agitation and loss of self-control

may need rapid tranquilization to decrease dangerous behaviour and allow treatment of the underlying psychiatric condition.

It becomes highly imperative for hospital nurses to coordinate health care service effectively with physicians, and to identify and recommend needed medications commonly used to reduce agitation such as lorazepam (alone or in combination with haloperidol) and atypical antipsychotics (olanzapine, risperidone, ziprasidone). Also, Nadler-Moodie (2010), maintained that hospital nurses must be familiar with the needed route of administration because some drugs are only available orally, some can be given intramuscularly, and haloperidol (lactate form only) is available for both intramuscular and intravenous use. Moreover, hospital nurses should be able to recognize symptoms of alcohol or drug abuse, and be able to distinguish between dementia and delirium that are common among hospitalized neurologic patients. The nurses should be able to maintain therapeutic relationships with patients who have neurologic symptoms. As prominent hospitals in Nigeria continue to experience an increase in individuals with neurologic ailments, being admitted to medical; surgical or intensive care units in the hospitals for complex and highly challenging health issues, educational programmes are needed to acquaint nurses with effective skills for effective management of these health challenges of neurologic patients.

(c) The Challenge of Working Environment of the Nurses:

Nurses in neurologic settings also face the challenge posed by their working environment. The World Health Organization (WHO), (2010) declared that the work environment constitutes an important factor in the recruitment and retention of health professionals and the characteristics of the work environment affect the quality of care both directly and indirectly. The working environment with regards to health care service refers to a set of concrete or abstract features of an organization, related to both the structures and processes in that organization that are perceived by nurses as either facilitating or constraining their professional practice.

According to Klopper et al.(2012), a healthy practice environment is a work setting where policies, procedures and systems

are designed in such a manner that they meet the organizational objectives and structures and processes in that organization, that are perceived by nurses as either facilitating or constraining their professional practice.

The overall goal of every ideal health care organization is to systematically develop and reinforce organizational strategies, structures and processes that improve the organisation's effectiveness in achieving quality patient care and employee job satisfaction. Therefore, it is quite expedient in Nigeria to link healthy work environment to patients' satisfaction, retention of health care givers increased attraction to health care service and enhancement of job satisfaction among health care givers. An environment without support for nurses performing professional practice hinders the delivery of good health care for patients. No wonder why nurses in Neurological Department usually hold the view that their professional working environment often appears onerous and stressful and this condition has a negative effect on their job satisfaction.

Establishing positive practice environments across health sectors in Nigeria is of paramount importance, if patient safety, and health workers' wellbeing are to be guaranteed. Such positive practice environments must be directed toward ensuring the health, safety and personal wellbeing of health care givers, support quality patient care and improve the motivation, productivity and performance of individuals and organizations. The working environment must be attractive and aesthetically pleasing to attract individuals into the health professions, encourage them to remain in the workforce and enable them to perform effectively.

(d) **The Challenge of Resources to work with.**

In carrying out neurological service effectively in hospitals, the nurses in such Neurological Departments require adequate provision of modern resources with which to carry out their neurological service. When modern equipment, tools and materials are adequately provided for neurological service, the morale of the nurses becomes enlivened and there is job satisfaction and high productivity. Moreover, drugs such as lorazepam, haloperidol, olanzapine, risperidone, ziprardone

and drugs to use to suppress disruptive and suicidal behaviours of hospitalized neurologic patients must be adequately and readily available in the intensive health care wards of the hospitals.

When nurses entrusted to neurologic service in hospitals are provided with adequate modern resources to work with, they are satisfied with their jobs, rates of absenteeism and turnover decrease, staff morale and productivity increase and work performance as a whole improves. Thus, safe and effective health care service to neurologic patients is directly and positively linked to the quality, adequacy and availability of resources with which to effectively carry out neurological service in hospitals.

Conclusions

The various needs and expectations of neurological work can be categorized into extrinsic and intrinsic motivation. The extrinsic motivation is related to tangible rewards such as salary and fringe benefits, security, promotion, contract of service, the work environment and conditions of works. These tangible rewards are often determined at the organizational level and may be largely outside the control of individual managers. The intrinsic motivation is related to psychological rewards such as the opportunity to use one's ability, a sense of challenge and achievement, receiving appreciation positive recognition and being treated in a caring and considerate manner. The psychological rewards are those that can usually be determined by the actions and behaviour of individual managers. The staff nurses would definitely perform impressively in their neurological service under conducive working environment, attractive conditions of service and provision of modern working equipments. Moreover, an efficient staff nurse is entitled to a commensurate salaries and allowances and attractive service conditions like his counterparts with identical, or similar qualifications and experience in the public service. It therefore becomes imperative for the Government and school administrators to be abreast of primary determinants of job satisfaction, which constitute the intrinsic aspects of job, called motivators such as achievement recognition, the work itself, responsibility, development and

advancement. These must be effectively administered to enhance the staff nurses' job satisfaction and productivity. While modern equipment for neurological services should be adequately provided.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made for improvement:

The Government should strive hard to make sufficient funds available for the provision of adequate facilities such as spacious, well illuminated and ventilated wards for the neurological patients and conducive and well furnished staff offices, portable water supply, modern toilet facilities, regular supply of electricity, well equipped laboratories, and internet services to enhance neurological service delivery and bring about high job satisfaction and productivity among the staff nurses.

All factors that can motivate the staff nurses productivity should be prioritized by the Government. These factors include attractive conditions of service, prompt disbursement of salaries and allowances, in-service training, delegation of authority, participatory leadership style of Heads of Neurological Departments, attractive and aesthetically pleasing staff office and working environment. These conditions would attract individuals into health professions, encourage them to remain in the workforce and perform effectively.

All registered nurses in Nigerian hospitals, especially those engaged in neurological service should be given regular patient education that will provide them adequate knowledge, information and improve their skills in attending to the health care delivery to their neurological patients.

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COMMUNICATION IN SPORTS: A VERITABLE TOOL IN SPORTS DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction

Communication is a vital concept in all areas of our lives and it is a crucial factor in any organisational effectiveness. This is because organisations cannot function effectively when communication skills are lacking among members of the organization, because we use it for persuasion, to influence relationships and decisions, to share, to inform, discover or uncover information. Since communication is the moving spirit in an organisation, its absence may cause organisations to be at a standstill. In sports organisations, communication provides the means by which the objectives or goals are accomplished.

Communication at a very conservative level is used in reference to man's transaction with other people. But on a much more liberal level, it is used in reference to man's transactions and his environment. Oriola and Akinjide (2000), believed that communication experts all over the world agreed that the concept is not a one-dimensional phenomenon but rather, a multidimensional process.